

Tongshu 通書

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Entry tags: Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region, Text, Chinese Religion, Religious Group, Neo-Confucian Traditions, Confucian (rujia 儒家) Traditions, Neo-Confucian text

Zhou Dunyi's Tongshu 通書 (Penetrating the Scripture of Change) is less well-known than the Taijitu shuo but is no less important for an understanding of Zhou Dunyi's thought. (For a brief account of Zhou Dunyi see the Entry Description of the Taijitu shuo.) The two works are very different in format: the Taijitu shuo is a single coherent essay, while the Tongshu as we have it today (in Zhu Xi's rescension) is composed of forty shorter, aphoristic, mostly independent pieces, each one with a title added by Zhu Xi. Furthermore, the central idea of each -- taiji 太極 (Supreme Polarity) in the Taijitu shuo and cheng 誠 (being authentic) in the Tongshu -- is not found at all in the other. Nevertheless, there are several important overlaps and no significant inconsistencies between the two texts, and I agree with Zhu Xi that they are products of the same author. "Penetrating the Scripture of Change" is a loose translation of the title, which more literally means "penetrating writing" or "penetrating the book." Zhu Xi averred that the original title was "Yi tongshu" 易通書, or "Book Penetrating the Yi," and most scholars have accepted that, as the text does refer to and quote the Yijing 易經 frequently. In fact it contains brief commentaries on nine of the sixty-four hexagrams of the Yi. While the Taijitu shuo is a philosophic cosmogony, situating human beings and in particular sages in the metaphysical and cosmological natural order, the Tongshu focuses in more detail on sagehood. Relying on both the Yijing and the Zhongyong 中庸 (Centrality and Commonality), it defines sagehood as "being authentic" (cheng). This term, usually but inadequately translated as "sincerity," has both a psychological and metaphysical meaning. On the simplest level it means having consistency between one's inner state and outward behavior. On this level "sincerity" is a somewhat superficial but adequate translation. However, even in the Zhongyong it is clear that cheng has a deeper meaning than "sincerity," and for this reason I translate it as "being authentic," in the sense of being real or genuine (shi 實), true to one's innate moral nature (xing 性) and fully embedded in the Way (dao 道), or fully aligned with li 理, the natural/moral order. Another major theme of the Tongshu is the importance of learning (xue 學) in the cultivation of sagehood, exemplified by Confucius' favorite disciple, Yan Hui 顏回.

Date Range: 1050 CE - 2021 CE

Region: Area of Circulation for the Taijitu Shuo and Tongshu (East Asia)

Region tags: Song Dynasty

Area of Circulation for the Taijitu Shuo and Tongshu (East Asia)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Zhou Dunyi 周敦頤. Zhou Lianxi xiansheng quanji 周濂溪先生全集 (Complete collection of Zhou Dunyi's works), comp. Zhang Boxing 張伯行. In Zhengyi tang quanshu 正誼堂全書 (Library of Zhengyi Hall [1708]). Baibu congshu jicheng ed., vols. 218-219.

- Source 2: Adler, Joseph A. *Reconstructing the Confucian Dao: Zhu Xi's Appropriation of Zhou Dunyi* (Albany: SUNY Press, 2014), ch. 7.
- Source 3: Fung Yu-lan, *A History of Chinese Philosophy*, trans. Derk Bodde, vol. 2 (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1953), 434-451.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://iep.utm.edu/zhou-dun/>
- Source 1 Description: Zhou Dunyi (Chou Tun-i, 1017-1073), by John Thompson (Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy)
- Source 2 URL: https://www.persee.fr/doc/etchi_0755-5857_2010_num_29_1_948
- Source 2 Description: Maud M'Bondjo, "Les notions de taiji 太極 et de cheng 誠 dans la pensée de Zhou Dunyi 周敦頤 (1017-1073): Parallélisme, identification et dissymétrie," *Etudes Chinoises* 29 (2010), 289-300.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/library.pl?if=en&file=87115&page=66>
- Source 1 Description: Tongshu, with commentary by Zhu Xi. In *Collected Papers of Zhou Dunyi*, comp. Zhang Boxing (Zhengyi tang ed.)

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Written

↳ Inked

- with Ink

Notes: Published in woodblock printing.

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

- Specify: Unknown

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Unknown

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Unknown

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is considered part of the scriptural canon defined by Zhu Xi (1130-1200). Whether that is "official" is a matter of interpretation.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: The Cheng-Zhu school of Confucianism itself was a reformist movement.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: 1. In the sense that the texts of the sages are canonical. 2. In Neo-Confucian anthologies (but, unlike the Taijitu shuo, not the Jinsilu or Song-Yuan xue'an): a. Xingli daquan shu 性理大全書 (Great Compendium of Nature and Principle), by Hu Guang b. Xingli jingyi 性理精義 (Essential Meanings of Nature and Principle), by Li Guangdi 3. It is included in the Daozang 道藏 (Daoist Canon)

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: The canon reflects Zhu Xi's construction of the "Learning of the Way" (Daoxue).

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

Notes: Not if one accepts the canon as defined by Zhu Xi.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– Yes

Notes: Zhu Xi's definition of the canon was not accepted by all scholars even in the Song dynasty. See, e.g. Hoyt Cleveland Tillman, *Confucian Discourse and Chu Hsi's Ascendancy* (Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 1992). And only since the late 20th century has it been acknowledged that Zhu Xi lifted Zhou Dunyi out of relative obscurity and made the Tongshu part of the Cheng-Zhu canon.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Song dynasty Confucian philosophy, specifically the Cheng-Zhu school.

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Notes: Although the various Confucian ritual texts set standards of moral behavior.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: Ritual and music are discussed but not specifically described.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Cheng-Zhu school of Neo-Confucianism, as constructed by Zhu Xi (1130-1200), also called

Daoxue (Learning of the Way).

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– No

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Intellectual Elect

Notes: Student-Teacher relationship also.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: Not in the sense of an ontological dichotomy, as in Western theology. But a difference between spirit (shen 神) and body (xing 形) is certainly acknowledged. They coexist on a continuum constituted by qi 氣 (psychophysical stuff).

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Ancestral spirits and ghosts are mentioned (e.g. sections 18 and 30).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

Notes: Ancestral spirits reside in Heaven (tian 天).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

Notes: Regarding ghosts and spirits: ghosts remain with the body in the earth, but if displeased they can wander and cause trouble. If "space" includes underground graves, then this is not "below space."

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: Ancestral spirits remain in Heaven as long as they are remembered and propitiated through ancestor worship.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions in the debate?

–Specify: Thinkers differ on whether ancestral spirits are aware of rituals performed for them.

Notes: See Thomas A. Wilson, "Spirits and the Soul in Confucian Ritual Discourse," *Journal of Chinese Religions*, 42:2 (2014), 185-212.

↳ What are the historically minority positions?

–Specify: Some believe that ancestral spirits have no consciousness.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Notes: "Heaven" (tian) comes close to being supernatural, but it is not ontologically distinct from nature. Ghosts and spirits are composed of the most rarefied forms of qi 氣 (psychophysical stuff), so in that respect, strictly speaking, they are not supernatural. All the entries below in this section refer to general beliefs about ghosts and spirits, not this text specifically. Most but not all the Confucians who regarded this text as scriptural would have subscribed to most but not necessarily all of these beliefs.

Reference: Joseph Adler A. "Varieties of Spiritual Experience: Shen in Neo-Confucian Discourse". (Weiming Tu , Mary Tucker Evelyn), *Confucian Spirituality*. New York: Continuum.

Reference: Daniel Gardner K. "Ghosts and Spirits in the Sung Neo-Confucian World: Chu Hsi on Kuei-shen". *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, 115(4)

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: "Ghosts and spirits" (gui-shen 鬼神) includes both dangerous spirits of the dead and benevolent ancestral spirits. While not specifically Confucian beliefs, these are part of the general worldview of traditional China (still today to some extent). Neo-Confucians tended to understand them in naturalistic ways as manifestations of qi 氣 (psychophysical stuff), which comprehends matter, energy, spirit, and mind. (See references under previous question.) There are sections on ghosts and spirits in the standard Neo-Confucian anthologies. In ancient China health and disease were understood as reward and punishment by deceased ancestors. By the Song dynasty this medical theory was declining in favor of natural causation, in terms of yin and yang qi. Ghosts (gui) are deceased spirits who have no descendants to nourish them with worship and food offerings, or whose descendants are ignoring these obligations, or who had not been buried in a ritually proper way. Ghosts therefore are dangerous but pitiable spiritual beings. Ancestral spirits can also be held responsible (usually by a spirit-medium) for a family's bad luck or recurring problems. One of the major Chinese holidays still today is the "Ghost Festival" in late summer, when communities set out feasts for wandering ghosts. Many businesses also set out food offerings for ghosts every 15 days, according to a traditional agricultural calendar (the 24 Qi 氣 or Solar Terms).

Reference: Stephen Teiser. *The Ghost Festival in Medieval China*. Princeton: Princeton University Press. isbn: 0691055254.

Human spirits can be seen

– Yes

Notes: This text doesn't specify, but in general spirits of the dead occasionally are seen.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: Beliefs in whether and how ghosts and spirits have knowledge of this world vary considerably. The belief that they can respond positively or negatively to their descendants' behavior implies that they do have such knowledge. Even in the naturalistic interpretation of Zhu Xi and his followers, "pure, numinous awareness" (xuling zhijue 虛靈知覺) is a function of qi 氣. Thus no special theory is required to explain it. As long as they are ritually remembered by their descendants, ghosts and spirits remain parts of the family.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: This depends on whether we are talking about an ancestor or a god. Both are considered to be spirits (shen 神). The difference is that the numinous power (ling 靈) of an ancestor is only great enough to affect his or her descendants. Gods have greater ling, so their power can affect a wider human circle, such as a community, a region, or even "all under Heaven" (tianxia 天下).

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region

– No

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– I don't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– I don't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– I don't know

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– I don't know

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– I don't know

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

–Specify: I don't know.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: See comments above.

↳ Human spirits can reward

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– No

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

Notes: Through shamans, or spirit-mediums, in popular religion. But this was a practice frowned upon by most Confucians.

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

Notes: Zhou Dunyi, in section 40 of the Tongshu, says "Divination is beseeching the spirits." Zhu Xi understood Yijing divination as a non-personal, naturalistic mechanism of "reading" the direction and flow of the Dao.

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Communicate through other means

–Specify: I don't know.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: "Natural spirits" are mentioned once (section 18), and non-specified spirits (which can also include ancestral spirits) are mentioned twice (sections 30 and 40).

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: I don't know.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: Many deities (included within "spirits") were formerly human.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be seen?

– No

Notes: Not under usual circumstances, although they can appear in dreams.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can be felt?

– I don't know

↳ Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living according to this text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– No

↳ In dreams?

– No

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– Yes

Notes: "Divination is beseeching the spirits" (section 40).

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ Other?

–Specify: No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: The Sage (shengren 聖人) represents the morally perfected human being, and is considered holy to a certain extent, but all people have the potential to become Sages.

Reference: Stephen Angle C.. Sagehood: The Contemporary Significance of Neo-Confucian Philosophy. New York: Oxford University Press. isbn: 9780195385144.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Yes

Notes: Three of the forty sections contain brief commentaries on nine of the sixty-four hexagrams of

the Yijing. One of those sections (40) includes one piece of guidance (don't ask the oracle a second or third time).

Reference: Joseph Adler A.. The Yijing: A Guide. New York: Oxford University Press.

↳ Divination by examination of the extra (animal remains)

– No

↳ Divination through human communication?

– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior?

– No

↳ Divination through non-living material?

– Other [specify]: Yarrow stalks or coins to derive Yijing hexagrams.

↳ Other form of divination:

– Specify: No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Most of the Confucian virtues are mentioned: humanity, rightness, ritual propriety, wisdom, honesty, being authentic, love of learning, love in general, reverent composure, impartiality.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned, authenticity (cheng 誠) and love of learning (xue 學). Authenticity, in Zhu Xi's interpretation, is the condition in which one's innate moral nature (xing 性), as defined by Mencius (4th c. BCE), is fully expressed in one's thought and action. (Zhu Xi's interpretation is most relevant because it was entirely due to him that Zhou Dunyi and his writings became canonical.) Thus Zhou Dunyi says, "Being a sage is nothing more than being authentic" (section 2). The innate moral nature is the human instantiation of the natural/moral order, or li 理, often translated as "principle." In this way the sage, who is perfectly authentic, is truly human and fully real.

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Notes: In addition to "honesty" (xin 信), "being authentic" (cheng 誠) can include the concept of integrity. It is often translated as "sincerity." According to the text (especially sections 1-4) it is the defining characteristic of the sage.

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Notes: "Humanity" (ren 仁), in the sense of being humane, is mentioned numerous times in the text, often in conjunction with rightness, ritual propriety, and wisdom. These four are the "four normative virtues" (si changde 四常德) discussed by Mencius.

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

Notes: Not specifically, but "humanity" (ren 仁) is defined by Mencius as the inability to bear suffering, and Zhou Dunyi presumably subscribed to that idea.

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Notes: "Ritual adherence" in the sense of ritual propriety (li 禮), but purity/impurity is not specifically mentioned.

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– No

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

Notes: Section 23, one of the longer sections, is an encomium to Yan Hui 顏回, or Master Yan, who was Confucius' favorite disciple. He was known for his love of learning and his frugality. Also section 33: "The superior person regards ceremonial carriages and caps as small change; he regards gold and jade as dust."

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

Notes: These things are not advocated; the superior person does not care for them.

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

Notes: Specifically optimism that sagehood can be learned.

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

Notes: Gratitude for simple necessities, like Master Yan.

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– I don't know

Notes: "Honesty" (xin 信) implies belief and trust.

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Notes: Especially being authentic (cheng 誠): thinking and acting in accordance with one's moral nature.

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: But it does praise Yan Hui's contentment with simple and meager food.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Notes: Not explicitly, but ritual propriety (li 禮) includes ancestor worship within the household.

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: They vary depending on the family.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Notes: It doesn't require participation, but it does discuss music in the context of large-scale state rituals (sections 17-19).

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: It doesn't specify, but ritual propriety assumes family ancestor worship involving offerings on an altar shelf or table.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Literati (scholars, intellectuals)

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Literati (scholars, intellectuals)

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: N/A

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: Education expanded greatly during the Song dynasty, partly due to the decreasing cost of woodblock printing. (Moveable type printing had been invented but was not used much because of the very large number of characters needed.) The central government sponsored the construction of schools in every county. There were also private academies established by prominent scholars such as Zhu Xi.

Reference: Hoyt Tillman, et. al.. Confucian Academies in East Asia. Leiden: BRILL. isbn: 978-90-04-42406-7.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Reference: Hoyt Tillman. Confucian Academies in East Asia. Leiden: Brill. isbn: 978-90-04-42406-7.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Not formally, but yes in practice. Education of girls was allowed but not required.

Reference: Bettine Birge. "Chu Hsi and Women's Education". (Wm. de Bary Theodore, John Chaffee W), Neo-Confucian Education: The Formative Stage. Berkeley: University of California Press.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Three of the forty sections of the Tongshu deal with teachers, who are to be honored and revered because they enable people to realize the Way (Dao).

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

Notes: Indirectly. "When worthy and talented men assist [the ruler], the empire will be well-governed" (section 12, on Government).

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– No

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– No

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– No

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Joseph Adler A. *Reconstructing the Confucian Dao: Zhu Xi's Appropriation of Zhou Dunyi*. Albany, NY: State University of New York Press. isbn: 1438451571.

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Reference: Yih-ching Chow. *La Philosophie Morale dans le Néo-Confucianisme* (Tcheou Touen-yi). Paris: Presses Universitaires de France.

Reference: Yulan Fung. *Chou Tun-i and Shao Yung*. (Yulan Fung, Derk Bodde, Ed.), *A History of Chinese Philosophy*. Princeton: Princeton University Press. isbn: 0691071152.

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Entry/Answer References

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